

INFLUENCE OF THE CARBON FIBRE SURFACE TREATMENT
ON THE MODE I FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN CFRP

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ABSTRACT

The bond between a fibre and the matrix is very important for the mechanical behaviour of the material. It will not only influence the ability to transfer stresses, but it will also influence the initiation and propagation of damage, like matrix cracking and delamination. If one assumes that flaws are always present inside a composite, the growth of the damage is governed by the fracture toughness of the material system. To study the influence of the interface properties on the fracture toughness of the composite, carbon fibres with four different oxidative treatment levels in an epoxy matrix were used. Mode I tests were performed using the DCB-test. Acoustic emission was used to establish the onset of delamination growth. Different data reduction techniques were used to calculate the delamination resistance curve. Results show a dramatic increase of the fracture toughness initiation value with increasing fibre surface treatment level (up to twice the value for the pure matrix). The propagation value however, reaches a maximum at intermediate treatment levels. A micromechanical model was developed to explain why the interface properties directly influence the initiation of the delamination. On the contrary, the propagation value is mainly influenced by the fibre bridging.

KEYWORDS: graphite, epoxy, interface, fracture toughness, mode I

1. INTRODUCTION.

Throughout the seventies and the eighties, fibre reinforced polymers have become well established. The use of different materials and the problems in the applications have led to a

big variety in different fibres and matrix materials. The properties of these basic materials, and their influence on the mechanical, physical and chemical properties of a composite have been thoroughly studied.

However, a composite material does not consist of two but three materials: fibre, matrix and interphase. The interphase is very important for two reasons. First, it acts as a binder between fibre and matrix: the interphase takes care of the stress transfer. Second, the interphase volume percentage is very high. In a unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite with 60 % fibres (with a diameter of $5\ \mu\text{m}$) of $1\ \text{cm}^3$, almost 3 million fibres are present, each of them surrounded by the interphase! In this way, the interface not only influences the mechanical properties of the material, but also the development of damage like matrix cracks and delaminations.

A carbon fibre is surface treated to get a good bond between the fibre and the matrix. A surface treatment creates active sites on the fibre surface which can react with the matrix material (primary or secondary bonds). It is well established that the surface treatment improves the bond with the matrix material, as can be measured during fragmentation or fibre pull out tests. This does not necessarily result in a better macromechanical performance of the composite. Some properties do improve, like the damage development during tensile loading of a cross ply laminate [1]: the transverse crack threshold increases strongly with increasing surface treatment of the carbon fibre. Because the first transverse cracks are generated at a defect (a small void, a debonding,...) the initiation and growth of these cracks is governed by the fracture toughness of the composite. Thus, an increase in fracture toughness with increasing fibre treatment could be expected. However, Norita et al. [2] and Lehman et al. [3] have found a decrease in mode I fracture toughness with increasing carbon fibre surface treatment.

The goal of this investigation is to study the influence of the interface strength on the fracture toughness of a composite. In this paper, attention is focussed on the mode I fracture toughness.

2. MATERIAL

IM 43-750 carbon fibres (strength: 5.5 GPa, E-modulus: 300 GPa) of Courtaulds were used for this study. The carbon fibres were surface treated by an oxidative treatment, in which four different treatment levels were used:

- 0% SST: untreated fibres
- 100% SST: commercially treated fibres
- 10% SST: fibres which received 10% of the normal commercial surface treatment
- 50% SST: fibres which received half of the normal surface treatment.

All fibres were sized.

The epoxy system used, was a toughened epoxy CG 9106.

Unidirectional laminates consisting of 24 plies (length 150 mm, width 20 mm) were made with a 50 mm aluminium crack starter between the mid plies. The plates were cured during 1.5 hours at 120°C and during 3 hours at 177°C, with a constant pressure of 7 bars. After curing, the quality of the plates was checked with the ultrasonic C-scanning technique.

3. TESTING PROCEDURE AND DATA ANALYSIS

The specimens were loaded in a mode I Double Cantilever Beam test (figure 1), on an Instron 6025 tensile testing machine. Before testing, a precrack was formed by growing a small crack from the aluminium foil. This was done to avoid the matrix rich zone in front of the aluminium. The initial crack was 40 mm long. A thin white coating and markings were put on the side of the specimen, to monitor the crack length at all times. The specimens were loaded until the crack length was 100 mm.

Figure 1: A DCB-test specimen with an initial crack length a .

The detection of the initiation point was done using acoustic emission. A sensor was placed on the specimen, and a AE signal threshold was chosen to reject the background noise of the machine. The initiation of the delamination occurred when the acoustic emission increases dramatically (figure 2).

Figure 2: Acoustic emission activity and load versus time. From this plot, the critical load P_c , at which initiation occurs, can be determined.

From load, displacement and crack length, the critical strain energy release rate G_{Ic} can be calculated, using the formula [4]:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{P_c^2}{2B} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \quad (1)$$

in which P_c is the critical load at which the crack grows, B is the width of the specimen, C is the compliance and a the crack length.

The data analysis was performed in three different ways. First the linear elastic beam theory was used [4]. This assumes a simple relation between the crack length a and the compliance C of the system:

$$C = \frac{8a^3}{Eh^3B} \quad (2)$$

with E the tensile modulus of the beam, and h the thickness of one beam (half the specimen thickness). This formula is called the LEFM (Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics) calculation. However, this relation does not take into account the shear deformation of the beam. Therefore, other data reduction methods have been developed which take these effects into account. One of them is the corrected beam theory, which makes a correction is by adding an fictitious crack length Δ to the real crack length, in order to take into account the above mentioned effects. Equation (1) is then replaced by:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3P\delta}{2B(a - \Delta)} \quad (3)$$

with δ the displacement. Δ can be measured as the intersection of the compliance plot with the crack length axis (figure 3a).

Figure 3a: Compliance vs crack length plot to determine the correction factor Δ ; figure 3b: logarithmic plot of compliance vs crack length to determine the Berry parameters n and h (R is the correlation coefficient)

Figure 4: Comparison of the three different data reduction methods used, for a typical specimen (0% SST)

The third method used is the Berry method. In this method, a calibration curve for the relation between the compliance and the crack length has to be generated.

$$C = \frac{a^n}{h} \quad (4)$$

For different crack lengths, the compliance is measured. Using the least squares method, the parameters n and h in (4) can be found from the log-log plot of crack length and compliance (figure 3b).

Figure 4 presents a typical crack resistance curve, calculated by the three data reduction methods. Figure 4 shows that the corrected LEFM method and the Berry method give similar results, whereas the values for the LEFM are significantly higher. This is because the shear deformation is not taken into account. Since both other methods give similar results, the corrected LEFM analysis will be used for all specimens because of its simplicity. From the crack resistance curve, a propagation value $G_{Ic,p}$ can be determined as the average of the crack propagation resistance from 80 to 120 mm.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results for the different surface treatments are shown in table 1 and figure 5. The initiation value increases with increasing surface treatment. The increase is very strong from 0 to 10 % SST. There is no significant difference between the material with the 10 and 50 % treated fibres, but again there is an important increase up to the 100 % material. The $G_{Ic,i}$ of the pure epoxy is 200 J/m², which means that only the material with untreated fibres has a lower fracture toughness.

treatment level	$G_{Ic,i}$ (J/m ²)	$G_{Ic,p}$ (J/m ²)
0 % SST	120 ± 25	530 ± 40
10 % SST	230 ± 45	830 ± 50
50 % SST	235 ± 35	900 ± 65
100 % SST	400 ± 10	640 ± 40

Table 1: Results of the mode I fracture toughness testing.

Figure 5: Results of the DCB tests: the initiation and propagation strain energy release rate as function of the fibre surface treatment level.

The propagation value reaches a maximum at a 50 % surface treatment level and decreases again for higher surface treatment levels like 100 %. During the tests, a high amount of fibre bridging has been observed in the specimens with low surface treatments. The fibre bridging decreased with increasing surface treatment.

4.1 Initiation of a delamination. Due to the accurate detection technique, the first initiation of the delamination is immediately monitored. The delamination growth will be influenced by the interface properties only, since all other influencing parameters, like the matrix fracture toughness, are kept constant in the experiments.

A model has been developed to predict the influence of the interface fracture toughness on the composite fracture toughness. The model is based on a model developed by Saghizadeh and Dharan [5]. If a hexagonal fibre array is assumed, three possible crack paths are possible (figure 6). Further assumptions made, are:

- stable crack growth, in which the crack follows the path of minimal energy absorption.
- plastic deformation has not been taken into account.
- no fibre splitting is occurring.

- matrix and interface have a constant fracture toughness (over the crack length)

The values of the mode II and mode III fracture toughness of matrix and interface are not known. Based on literature [6], the following ratio's are assumed:

$$G_{Ic} : G_{IIc} : G_{IIIc} = 3 : 7 : 10 \quad (5)$$

In the model, the heterogeneity of the composite is taken into account. A perfectly homogeneous laminate has a homogeneity factor 1. In the material used in the study, the original bundle structure is still visible. For this special case, the homogeneity factor corresponds to the bundle volume fraction. For these laminates, this corresponds to a factor of 0.85.

Figure 6: Schematic presentation of the composite, with the three possible crack paths: the hexagonal path (top), matrix crack path (middle), linear crack path (bottom).

The fibre volume fraction within a bundle is $V_f/0.85 = V_f$.

At point a (figure 6), a pure mode I load exists. However, on point b, the load is pure mode III. In between these two extremes, a mixed mode I and III exists. The strain energy release rate is:

$$G_{tot} = G_I + G_{III} \quad (6)$$

The angle θ between the actual loading point (point c in figure 6) and pure mode I (point a) determines the amount of mode I and mode III. Saghizadeh and Dharan used a goniometric correlation:

$$G_{tot,c} = G_{Ic} \cos \theta + G_{IIIc} \sin \theta \quad (7)$$

Others predict a linear relation:

Figure 7: the two hypotheses for the mixed mode fracture toughness used.

$$G_{\text{tot,c}} = G_{\text{Ic}} \frac{\pi - 2\theta}{\pi} + G_{\text{IIIc}} \frac{2\theta}{\pi} \quad (8)$$

Both hypotheses are shown graphically in figure 7.

The hypothesis which corresponds best to the real situation, will be used. Mixed mode I and II tests performed by Albertsen and Peters [7] did not show a linear relation. It is most likely that mixed mode I and III will not have a linear relation either. Therefore, only the non-linear relation will be calculated.

4.1.1. Pure matrix crack. The crack path is shown in figure 6. The following value for the composite fracture toughness was found:

$$G_{\text{tot,c}} = G_{\text{IMc}} \left(1 + Y_{\text{M}}^{13} (2 - \sqrt{3}) \right) \quad (9)$$

in which G_{IMc} is the mode I critical strain energy release rate of the matrix and Y_{M}^{13} is the ratio of $G_{\text{IIIC}}/G_{\text{IMC}}$

4.1.2. Linear interface crack. The crack path is also shown in figure 6 (bottom). The composite fracture toughness can be calculated from:

$$G_{\text{tot,c}} = G_{\text{IM,c}} \left(\frac{D}{\Delta} S \left(\sin \alpha + Y_{\text{i}}^{13} (1 - \cos \alpha) \right) + \left(1 - \frac{D}{\Delta} \sin \alpha \right) \right) \quad (10)$$

With: Y_{i}^{13} : ratio of $G_{\text{IIIC}}/G_{\text{IC}}$ of the interface.

$$\alpha = \text{bgtg} \left(\frac{1 - S}{S Y_{\text{i}}^{13}} \right) \quad (11)$$

4.1.3. Hexagonal crack path. This is shown in figure 6 (top). In the same manner as above, the fracture toughness can be calculated:

$$G_{\text{tot,c}} = \frac{2D}{\Delta} \int_0^{\alpha} \left[G_{\text{Ii,d}} \left(1 - \frac{2\theta}{\pi} \right) + G_{\text{IIIi,d}} \left(\frac{2\theta}{\pi} \right) \right] d\theta + h \left[G_{\text{Im,d}} \left(1 - \frac{2\beta}{\pi} \right) + G_{\text{IIIIm,d}} \left(\frac{2\beta}{\pi} \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

with

$$h = \sqrt{\Delta^2 + D^2 - 2D\Delta \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{6} - \alpha \right)} \quad (13)$$

$$\beta = \text{bg} \cos \left(\frac{\frac{\Delta}{2} - D \sin \alpha}{h} \right) \quad (14)$$

The angle α must be calculated, using formula (15)

$$DS \left[1 + \frac{\alpha}{\pi} (Y_i^{13} - 1) \right] + \frac{dh}{d\alpha} + \frac{2}{\pi} (Y_m^{13} - 1) \left[h \frac{d\beta}{d\alpha} + \beta \frac{dh}{d\alpha} \right] = 0 \quad (15)$$

with

$$\frac{dh}{d\alpha} = \frac{-\Delta D \sin \left(\frac{\pi}{6} - \alpha \right)}{h} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{d\beta}{d\alpha} = \frac{hD \cos \alpha + \left(\frac{\Delta}{2} - D \sin \alpha \right) \frac{dh}{d\alpha}}{h^2 \sin \beta} \quad (17)$$

The composite mode I fracture toughness for the three different crack paths is shown in figure 8 . The crack path corresponding to the path of the lowest energy absorption will be followed (bold line).

The jumps in the two different models are caused by the fact that, at a certain interface fracture toughness, this particular crack path becomes impossible.

The model shows the same tendency as the evolution of the experimentally observed composite fracture toughness as a function of the fibre surface treatment: a sharp increase for low interface fracture toughness, followed by a zone in which the slope is low. Finally, the composite fracture toughness jumps to higher values. In reality, this jump will not be discrete, because of small defects and local variations in fibre volume fraction..

4.2 Propagation of a delamination. The propagation of the delamination is strongly influenced by fibre bridging. This decreases with increasing fibre treatment, because the shear strength of the interface increases. The increased interfacial shear strength results in higher energy storage in the fibre and after debonding, in energy absorption by friction

during fibre pull out. These effects will result in an increased propagation value. However, if the interfacial strength becomes too high, the carbon fibres will break, like it is observed during a fibre pull out test. This means that no friction effects will take place, and less energy will be absorbed during crack propagation.

Figure 8: Mode I strain energy release rate of the composite as a function of the mode I strain energy release rate of the interface for the three different crack paths. The bold line shows the path of minimal energy absorption.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The influence of the interface on the composite fracture toughness has been investigated. Three different data reduction methods were used. The corrected LEFM method was used to calculate the crack resistance curve for the different materials.

The initiation value increases with increasing surface treatment. A model has been developed to explain this influence. The model shows how the interface strength influences the crack path, and thus the fracture toughness. It also explains the shape of the curve: an important increase in toughness going from 0 to 10 % SST, and another increase from 50 to 100 % SST, whereas the values for 10 and 50 % are not significantly different.

The propagation fracture toughness is influenced by the interface strength and by the fibre bridging effect. The latter decreases with increasing surface treatment, although the energy absorbed by each pulled out fibre increases with increasing surface treatment. Both effects result in a maximum propagation fracture toughness at intermediate surface treatment levels.

6. REFERENCES

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